

Adaptability and Teaching Performance of Gulod and Mamatid National High School Teachers During the Pandemic

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to assess teachers' performance and adaptability at two public schools in Cabuyao, Laguna, Philippines, in 2021-2022. It attempted to determine the level of adaptability and performance skills, such as self-awareness, personal management, problem and decision-making, attitude, and competence grasp, that teachers need to deal with the fast-changing academic environment. This study also investigated whether the adaptability of instructors varies based on their profiles. It intended to bridge the gap by examining how instructors' adaptation skills relate to their performance. The study aimed to determine how teachers were able to respond to changes and student needs and provide potential solutions. The research utilized the comparative and descriptive-correlational approach, and 118 high school teacher answers were collected. The statistical analysis used the frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, z-test for independent samples, one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's product-moment correlation. The findings revealed that female teachers between the ages of 31 and 40 with less than six years of teaching experience made up most of the study. The findings also revealed that teachers scored well in areas linked to training. It was also discovered that teachers could swiftly adapt to any characteristic of the modern learning environment. When they were categorized based on their profiles and campus, their levels of adaptability did not alter much. The capacity to adjust and teaching performance had no significant correlation. Future studies may be conducted to elucidate other variables and encourage institutional management for programs and initiatives.

Keywords: Adaptability, Teachers' Adaptability, Performance, Pandemic

INTRODUCTION

The education sector is one of the major industries being impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic. In this setting, online learning demonstrated a pedagogical movement from the traditional technique toward a more technological teaching style. Teachers' motivation and performance might deteriorate due to the educational sector's catastrophic upheaval and the pandemic's disruptive effects, which may linger longer in the educational community (Onyema et al., 2020). Educators were expected to overcome their obstacles with online learning as part of this adaptation process (Safta-Zecheria et al., 2020). Therefore, teachers must analyze their level of flexibility since it might affect their student's long-term development.

Koc and Fidan (2022) argued that complex tasks for public and private school teachers include managing online classrooms, providing materials and activities, adapting curricula for distance learning, making important themes concrete for students studying social sciences, and providing materials and activities. This argued that educators must be prepared to adapt to the environmental changes caused by the pandemic. Therefore, teachers may adapt in various ways depending on their profiles and abilities. A teacher's flexibility and performance may be associated with their profile factors, including age, gender, position, and educational attainment.

Teachers must adapt to these changes to provide high-quality education and maintain good performance

in the face of this pandemic, which may impact students' knowledge and learning. According to Dhanush et al. (2023), instructors employed various coping techniques to deal with the stress and uncertainty generated by the pandemic, including seeking social support, maintaining a positive attitude, and prioritizing their own needs. Thus, instructors could fulfill their tasks efficiently because of their optimism and resilience under duress (Lagat, 2021). Understanding how flexibility impacts a teacher's effectiveness in the classroom is critical. It was also examined to discover whether adaptability varies in response to potentially affecting events.

In this manner, the study aimed to discover how teachers managed the shift to online learning in the face of pandemic concerns. The goal was to determine how teachers' effectiveness in their roles is connected to their adaptation skills, which include self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making, attitude, and competence knowledge. It demonstrated how educators may meet the needs of children while overcoming their obstacles. The study tried to reduce the gap by investigating whether teachers' degrees of adaption alter depending on their profiles. It also aimed to close the knowledge and skill gap between students' knowledge and skills and the outcomes of their changes.

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Figure 1. The Conceptual Framework of the Study as to the Difference of Teachers' Adaptability Skills when grouped according to Profile

Figure 2. The Conceptual Framework of the Study as to the Relationship between Teachers' Adaptability Skills and Teaching Performance

The correlation of teaching performance and adaptability of teachers at Gulod National High School [GNHS] and Mamatid National High School [MNHS] in 2021-2022 were evaluated. This study also compared the adaptability skills of the respondents according to their profiles and designated school.

Conceptual Framework

The first framework shows the predictor variable, teachers' demographic profile in terms of age, sex, teaching experience, and designated school; and outcome variable, teachers' adaptability skills. The arrow that connects between them implies a test whether the teachers' adaptability skills differ according to their age, sex, teaching experience, and designated school.

The second framework includes the predictor variable, teachers' adaptability skills in terms of self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making, attitude, and knowledge of competencies; and the outcome variable, teaching performance of teachers based on the IPCRF rating. The

line that connects them signifies a test whether teachers' adaptability skills have association with the teaching performance of teachers.

Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the level of adaptability skills of the teachers when grouped according to their profiles and school.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between the teachers' level of adaptability skills and their teaching performance.

Literature Review and Framework

This study is based on the adaptation theory, which contends that organisms may adapt to and react to environmental changes throughout time (King, 2018). Cherry described adaptation as becoming used to new information and experiences. Learning includes adapting to a changing environment. Cherry highlighted Jean Piaget's theory that adaptability is required for cognitive growth. Assimilation or accommodation may lead to adaptability.

People initially absorb information from their surroundings into their thoughts and ideas. The second is to alter mental representations of newly acquired knowledge (Cherry, 2021).

This study is also supported by the career creation theory, which helps people choose and use jobs. The theory examines occupational behavior across the life cycle and provides career counselors with tools to help clients choose occupations and thrive at work. Three views on vocational behavior are used to assure its thoroughness: differential, developmental, and dynamic. Counselors and researchers can use the three techniques to investigate how individuals use life themes to integrate personality self-organization and career adaptability into a self-defining totality that animates work, directs occupational choice, and determines vocational adjustment (Savickas, 1997).

Individuals adapt in various settings owing to change, novelty, and changes by modifying their ideas, behaviors, and emotions by adapting to examine the possibilities in the new environment, which is consistent with an individual's adaptability to changes in their environment (Collie et al., 2018). Therefore, the position of teachers in the new online learning environment has been described as transitional or ambiguous. In response to these changes, instructors adopt a new approach to their work performance, instructional strategies, and learning style.

COVID-19 greatly influences everyone, most especially the education sector. Adaptability is critical for teachers because it will necessitate adjusting thinking and attitudes about how students learn online and how technology can be harnessed in novel ways in teaching, adjusting behaviors by seeking technical support for remote teaching, and adjusting emotions by reining in potential anxiety or frustration as new technologies are navigated, and different students engage with remote learning in unique ways (Collie & Martin, 2020).

Thus, instructors must adapt to students' needs, such as coping with unexpected classroom settings or scheduling changes, communicating with new colleagues, students, and parents, and integrating new and changing professional education into teaching (Collie et al., 2018). Instructors' adaptability to their new surroundings permits them to adjust to new difficulties. This will also help pupils avoid barriers and substantial impediments in their new surroundings or learning style.

Given the need for adaptability, it is hard to deny that there have been instances of work disengagement since not all educators can adjust to changes that occur. However, job disengagement happens when teachers work but then leave (Collie & Martin, 2018). Hence, initiatives and attempts to help teachers adapt to their new conditions are required. Focusing only on teachers' flexibility may be easier for them if there is aid or cooperation from the school system to help them overcome these problems. Teachers' flexibility should be developed in collaboration with everyone in the education sector to help them in their job performance.

Castillo (2021) examines the class observation experiences of junior high school teachers during COVID-19 in a specific scenario. He noticed that instructors observe classes for two reasons: improving teachers' service competency and guaranteeing that policy standard are followed despite field modifications. There have also been instances when instructors showed amazing patience and commitment in dealing with difficulties during an online discussion due to inadequate internet signal and other technicalities. Cooperation in education is crucial since instructors find adapting to the current environment challenging if educational administration agencies or organizations need to help with this issue. Leaders and teachers must collaborate closely to adapt to the present situation.

Despite the challenges posed by the pandemic and changes in the learning environment, some studies have found that instructors have a strong sense of adaptability to the current situation. Munda (2021) observed that teachers were highly adaptable regarding self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making, attitude, and competent knowledge. Meanwhile, female teachers were found to be less adaptable, although those above 50 were very adaptable. Similarly, Andres et al. (2021) argued that instructors are flexible teachers in a fast-changing academic environment.

Adapting to the usage of technological components is as important as adapting to skills and performance. According to Mardiana (2020), most instructors embrace online education and new methods to equip them for 21st-century online learning. Similarly, teacher competency in ICT tools is essential because it allows them to be adaptable to the transition to online education (Konig, Jager-Biela, & Glutch, 2020).

With the given circumstances, the instructors' abilities included adaptation. The research revealed the importance of teachers' adaption skills and how they may be managed and used. It highlighted how teachers might use adaptation skills to react to changes in the school environment caused by the outbreak. The study aims to fill a knowledge gap on how adaptability relates to teachers' job performance. It will evaluate the association of their adaptability skills on their work performance, particularly self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making, Attitude, and Knowledge of Competencies.

Furthermore, the study intends to discover the gap by determining if teachers' adaption capacities differ depending on their profiles. It also aims to close the gap between the outcomes of their adaptation to their student's learning and skills. Therefore, the study will underline the need for flexibility in reacting to changes in the new environment.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the comparative and descriptive-correlational design. The descriptive design includes

the profile of the teachers as to age, sex, and teaching experience, teachers' performance based on the latest Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form [IPCRF] rating, and level of adaptability skills of the teachers. The researcher also got the difference in the adaptability skills of the teachers when grouped according to their profiles. Meanwhile, the correlational design includes the test if there is a relationship between the level of adaptability skills of the teachers and their teaching performance.

Population and Sampling

The target participants were 118 out of 169 teachers. The researcher used multi-stage cluster sampling to select the participants of the study, where samples were drawn from a population using smaller groups at each stage. The sample size was determined by using the Raosoft online calculator, with 56 out of 80 and 62 out of 89 teacher-respondents at GNHS and MNHS, respectively.

Instrumentation

Demographics, teaching performance rating, and adaptability were used in a survey questionnaire. The researcher employed Morgan's (2011) adaptation survey. Subject matter experts evaluated the instrument's content validity. The questionnaire's Cronbach's alpha ($\alpha = 0.90$) showed "Excellent reliability" (Munda and Tamban, 2019). Before survey, the researcher needs ethical clearance. The researcher asked for the Superintendent and schools heads' permission. Following research ethics, ethical committee criteria were followed. Data collection requires ethics committee approval. Confidentiality, anonymity, and voluntary participation are required. Thus, researcher provided informed consent to the respondents.

Statistical Analysis

The researcher employed frequency and percentage to determine the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of sex, age, and teaching experience. Weighted mean and standard deviation were used to describe the teaching performance and adaptability of the respondents. Regarding the significance of the difference between two and more than two groups, the z-test for independent samples and one-way analysis of variance were respectively employed. Lastly, Pearson r was utilized to examine the link between the level of adaptation skills and teachers' performance ratings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part of the research shows how the findings were presented and discussed following the topic. Among the results were teacher profiles, performance levels, adaption levels, significant difference tests, and correlations between instructors based on profile and performance.

Table 1 presents the profile of the teachers in terms of age, sex, and teaching experience. The respondents with an age range of 31 to 40 are dominant in this study (49 or 41.5%). On the other hand, the least of the age group belongs to those 51 years old and above (7.9% or 5.9%). It also shows that female teachers (85, or 72%) are more dominant in this study than male teachers (33, or 28.0%). Concerning years of teaching experience, most participants have less than six years of experience (54 or 45.8%), while the least belong to 21 years and above (2 or 1.7%). Women outnumbered males in the teacher profile findings because women are substantially overrepresented in the teaching profession (Tani, 2019). In a similar situation, there were more instructors in their middle years than in other age groups and more professors with less than six years of

Table 1. The Profile of Teachers in terms of Age, Sex, and Teaching Experience

Profile	Frequency	Percent
Age		
21 – 30 years old	38	32.2
31 – 40 years old	49	41.5
41 – 50 years old	24	20.3
51 years old and above	7	5.9
Total	118	100.0
Sex		
Male	33	28.0
Female	85	72.0
Total	118	100.0
Teaching Experience		
Less than 6 years	54	45.8
6 - 10 years	39	33.1
11 – 15 years	19	16.1
16 – 20 years	4	3.4
21 years and above	2	1.7
Total	118	100.0

Table 2. The Teachers' Teaching Performance Level

Rating	Frequency	Percent	Mean	Std Dev	Interpretation
1.500 – 2.499	2	1.7			
2.500 – 3.499	9	7.6			
3.500 – 4.499	96	81.4	4.11	0.43	Very Satisfactory
4.500 – 5.000	11	9.3			
Total	118	100.0			

Legend: 4.500-5.000 Outstanding; 3.500-4.499 Very Satisfactory; 2.500-3.499 Satisfactory; 1.500-2.499 Unsatisfactory; Below 1.499 Poor

classroom experience.

Table 2 depicts the profile of the teachers in terms of years of the teachers' performance based on the latest IPCRF rating. The table shows that most of the participants have a performance rating from 3.500 to 4.499 (96 or 81.4%), while there are only 2 or 1.7% of participants who have a rating between 1.500 and 2.499. Further, there are no participants with ratings below 1.499. The overall mean of participants in terms of their performance rating is 4.11 (SD = 0.43), with an interpretation of "very satisfactory". It signifies that the respondents to this study have a very satisfactory level of performance.

Given the instructors' performance level, it became evident that, despite the online learning environment, teachers can adjust to it and work magnificently. It revealed that teachers are competent in handling a diverse range of students in this new manner of learning, paying attention to student's needs, and working efficiently. It revealed how effective teachers were at adapting to changing circumstances while maintaining a high level of performance that pleased the students.

Table 3 displays the level of adaptability skills of the teachers at GNHS and MNHS. In terms of self-awareness, the statements with the highest means are "I have a vision for my life that gives it meaning and purpose" ($x = 4.47$, $SD = 0.58$), and "I know what is important to me and use this knowledge in making decisions" ($x = 4.47$, $SD = 0.55$), with shared interpretation "High level". On the other hand, the statement with the least mean is "I have a strong sense of self-esteem and generally feel good about myself" ($x = 3.95$, $SD = 0.67$), with an interpretation "High level". The respondents' overall mean on self-awareness is 4.18 (SD = 0.46). Concerning the respondents' personal management, the statement with the highest mean is "I take responsibility for managing my studies" ($x = 4.60$, $SD = 0.53$), with an interpretation "Very high level". In contrast, the statement with the least mean is "I have a personal financial plan which I evaluate regularly based on my current situation" ($x = 4.07$, $SD = 0.71$), with an interpretation "High level". The respondents' overall mean on personal management is 4.26 (SD = 0.50). In terms of the respondents' problem-solving and decision-making, the statement with the highest mean is "I have emerged stronger and have learned personal strategies to deal with change because of the changes in my life" ($x = 4.24$, $SD = 0.57$), with an interpretation "High level". Conversely, the statement with the least mean is "When experiencing stress in one area of life, I can contain it within that area" ($x = 4.02$, $SD =$

0.68), with an interpretation "High level". The respondents' overall mean on problem-solving and decision-making is 4.13 (SD = 0.52). Regarding the respondents' attitude, the statement with the highest mean is "I expect life to have ups and downs and not always go as I would like it to" ($x = 4.68$, $SD = 0.49$), with an interpretation "Very high level". Alternatively, the statement with the least mean is "I don't spend time worrying about things that are out of my control" ($x = 4.09$, $SD = 0.76$), with an interpretation "High level". The respondents' overall mean on attitude is 4.40 (SD = 0.45). Concerning the respondents' knowledge of competencies, the statement with the highest mean is "I would describe myself as a continuous learner" ($X = 4.55$, $SD = 0.58$), with an interpretation "Very high level". In contrast, the statement with the least mean is "I know what others in our school expect of me" ($x = 3.95$, $SD = 0.69$), with an interpretation "High level". The respondents' overall mean on knowledge of competencies is 4.20 (SD = 0.48). Lastly, the respondents have the highest mean value on attitude ($x = 4.40$, $SD = 0.45$), while they have got a least mean value on problem-solving and decision-making. The respondents' have high level of adaptability ($x=4.24$, $SD = 0.40$).

Findings showed a high level of adaptability in terms of self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making skills, competency comprehension, and attitude in the face of a pandemic. It also underlines how adaptability and flexibility in a new kind of learning environment might assist educators in overcoming the epidemic's challenges. Teachers have changed their course designs and teaching practices to meet the problem of the learning environment.

Table 4 presents the test of significant difference in teachers' level of adaptability skills in terms of age, which shows that teachers with ages 51 years and older obtained the highest mean level (4.42) compared to other age groups. Though all age groups obtained high levels of adaptability, teachers between 21 and 30 years old have the lowest mean (4.18) among the respondents. However, the results of the one-way ANOVA show no significant difference in the level of adaptability skills of the teachers in terms of age ($F = 1.84$, $p = 0.14$). It also shows that, though both groups fall into high-level interpretation, male teachers have a greater mean score (4.30) than females (4.20). Nevertheless, the results of independent samples z-test show no significant difference in teachers' level of adaptability skills in terms of sex ($z = 1.19$, $p = 0.23$). Munda's (2021) study also had relatively similar results; male (4.28) respondents appeared to have a higher mean value on adaptability than female

Table 3. The Level of Adaptability Skills of Teachers

	Statement	Mean	SD	Interpretation
1	I can articulate my special abilities, talents, and skills.	4.04	0.65	High level
2	I know what I must do to regain my confidence when I temporarily lose it.	4.10	0.65	High level
3	I have a strong sense of self-esteem and generally feel good about myself.	3.95	0.67	High level
4	I can identify and communicate my weaknesses and the ways that I work with or around them.	4.03	0.69	High level
5	I have a vision for my life that gives it meaning and purpose.	4.47	0.58	High level
6	I know what is important to me and use this knowledge in making decisions.	4.47	0.55	High level
Self-awareness		4.18	0.46	High level
7	I take responsibility for managing my (graduate) studies.	4.60	0.53	Very high level
8	I can see how my study fits into the bigger picture of my life plans.	4.33	0.65	High level
9	I have a personal financial plan which I evaluate regularly based on my current situation.	4.07	0.71	High level
10	I have contingency plans, a second option if my first plan doesn't work out.	4.15	0.68	High level
11	I assess my strengths and weaknesses, outline ways to grow, and establish short- and long-range goals for my (graduate) studies.	4.16	0.67	High level
Personal Management		4.26	0.50	High level
12	I have emerged stronger and have learned personal strategies to deal with change because of the changes in my life.	4.24	0.57	High level
13	I can organize my surroundings and prioritize tasks, even in stressful times.	4.14	0.61	High level
14	I can find and mobilize necessary resources in a crisis or new situation.	4.16	0.64	High level
15	I can usually think of several alternatives to solving a problem.	4.11	0.62	High level
16	When experiencing stress in one area of life, I can contain it within that area.	4.02	0.68	High level
Problem-solving and Decision-making		4.13	0.52	High level
17	I believe that I always have options and choices, even in difficult situations.	4.47	0.60	High level
18	I generally approach life as an optimist.	4.36	0.61	High level
19	I have a sense of humor. I can find things to laugh about even in dark times.	4.21	0.73	High level
20	I understand there is growth in new experiences and enjoy learning from them.	4.58	0.54	Very high level
21	I expect life to have ups and downs and not always go as I would like it to.	4.68	0.49	Very high level
22	I don't spend time worrying about things that are out of my control.	4.09	0.76	High level
Attitude		4.40	0.45	High level
23	I would describe myself as a continuous learner.	4.55	0.58	Very high level
24	I regularly spend time keeping my knowledge and skills current.	4.23	0.61	High level
25	I know the skills that will be required in my studies in the next several years.	4.25	0.60	High level
26	I know what others in our school expect of me.	3.95	0.69	High level
27	I know how my current skills are viewed by my co-teachers.	4.03	0.77	High level
28	I know which behaviors and attitudes are rewarded in our school.	4.21	0.64	High level

Knowledge of Competencies	4.20	0.48	High level
Overall Level of Adaptability	4.24	0.40	High level

Legend: 4.50 – 5.00 Very high level; 3.50 – 4.49 High level; 2.50 – 3.49 Average level; 1.50 – 2.49 Fair level; 1.00 – 1.49 Poor level of Adaptability

Table 4. Test of Difference in the Level of Adaptability Skills of the Teachers when grouped according to their Profiles and School

Profile	Mean	SD	VI	CV	P-value	Interpretation
Age						
21 – 30 years old	4.18	0.37	High level			
31 – 40 years old	4.19	0.38	High level	1.84	0.14	Not significant
41 – 50 years old	4.36	0.42	High level			
51 years old and above	4.42	0.54	High level			
Sex						
Male	4.30	0.37	High level	1.19	0.23	Not significant
Female	4.20	0.41	High level			
Teaching Experience (Years)						
Less than 6 years	4.15	0.37	High level			
6 - 10 years	4.32	0.39	High level	2.08	0.09	Not significant
11 – 15 years	4.24	0.44	High level			
16 – 20 years	4.24	0.51	High level			
21 years and above	4.82	0.26	Very high level			
Designated School						
Gulod NHS	4.21	0.38	High level	-1.12	0.26	Not significant
Mamatid NHS	4.29	0.44	High level			

Legend: SD=Standard Deviation, CV=Computed Value; 4.50 – 5.00 Very high level; 3.50 – 4.49 High level; 2.50 – 3.49 Average level; 1.50 – 2.49 Fair level; 1.00 – 1.49 Poor level of Adaptability; Significant if p-value is < 0.05

teachers (4.21). In terms of teaching experience, the results show that teachers with teaching experience of 21 years and above have the highest mean (4.82), while those with less than 6 years of teaching experience have the lowest mean (4.15). Further, the results of the one-way ANOVA show no significant difference in the teachers' level of adaptability in terms of years of teaching experience ($F = 2.08, p = 0.09$). Lastly, the teachers at MNHS got a higher mean score (4.29) than the GNHS teachers (4.21). The test of difference further revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in the adaptability of the teachers as to their designated school ($z = -1.12, p = 0.26$).

Table 5 displays the test of the relationship between the level of teaching adaptability skills of the teachers and their job performance based on their individual performance commitment and review form rating. Using Pearson r , the correlation values range from 0.21 to 0.81, which are all greater than the significance level (0.05). It signifies that the null hypotheses were retained. Thus, there was no significant relationship between the level of adaptability skills of the teachers and their performance based on the IPCRF rating.

DISCUSSION

Based on the findings, most instructors who participated in this survey were women between 31 and

40 who had taught for less than 6 years. Munda's (2021) study on the adaptability of public-school teachers during the pandemic found that most of his respondents were 31 to 35 years old, while Asio's (2021) study featured teacher respondents who were 21 to 30 years old. Furthermore, the mean age of the Andres et al. (2021) research is 37, with instructors aged 20 to 30 having the greatest mean. Furthermore, most respondents in Munda's study were female teachers, whereas male teachers predominated in Asio's study. Most respondents in Munda's and Asio's studies had 1 to 5 years of teaching experience.

Teachers are doing well regarding teaching-related performance, even amid the COVID-19 epidemic. Having ratings between 3.500 and 4.499 necessitates instructors working hard even while working from home or in a face-to-face setting. It was supported by the study of Andres et al. (2021), which found that 63% of their respondents performed very satisfactorily, while 36% performed outstandingly. It also implies that the instructors are doing better.

A high level of performance also demonstrated that they have a feeling of importance and direction in their self-awareness. Instructors' self-awareness is generally reflected in their favorable attitude toward themselves. Personal management has also been a good component for the instructors, as they were able to establish preparations

Table 5. Test of Relationship between Teachers' Level of Adaptability Skills and their Performance based on the IPCRF Rating

Independent Variable	r value	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Self-awareness	-0.10	0.28	Failed to reject Ho	Not significant
Personal Management	-0.12	0.21	Failed to reject Ho	Not significant
Problem-solving and Decision-making	-0.09	0.33	Failed to reject Ho	Not significant
Attitude	-0.02	0.81	Failed to reject Ho	Not significant
Knowledge of Competencies	-0.09	0.33	Failed to reject Ho	Not significant
Overall Adaptability	-0.10	0.27	Failed to reject Ho	Not significant

Legend: Significant if $p < 0.05$

for their graduate courses and examine personal financial goals, and personal growth, demonstrating their high level of productivity. Also, problem-solving and decision-making revealed that teachers could become more resilient and develop unique coping mechanisms that allow them to manage changes in their lives better. It shows that teachers have strong decision-making abilities and problem-solving management skills, which help them more efficiently manage their lives. One of the components to examine is attitude, which shows that instructors anticipate the possibilities and repercussions. Regarding adaptability, attitude is a crucial component to understand since it will assist them in minimizing negativity and offer a positive view of the changes occurring. Finally, teachers believed that a strong knowledge of competencies would be achieved by being aware of the expectations that others in their school have of them. Findings showed that instructors strongly expressed all the components in determining their degree of adaptability, which aids them in overcoming the changes that occur in the new learning environment.

In a similar case, Munda (2021) demonstrated that teachers are adaptable by transitioning from face-to-face instruction to blended and modular distance instruction, distributing modules and weekly home learning plans, retrieving students' answer sheets, maintaining virtual communication with students, parents, and guardians, and attending virtual seminars. Despite increasing non-job-related obligations, instructors remained dependable and adaptive (Andres et al., 2021). Teachers were competent to educate and adapt to the changing academic environment as new instructional approaches emerged.

Teachers' adjustment and adaptation abilities also involve being flexible in the online style of education. Teachers were strengthening their online teaching and abilities via ICT technologies, competence, and the opportunity to gain digital skills critical to their transition due to school closures (Mardiana, 2020). Further, adherence to service competence and school policy compliance is also essential when developing their adaptability skills (Castillo, 2021). Teachers were able to become more adaptable with the help and participation of leaders and school heads. Collie and Martin (2018) discovered that instructors who get greater assistance from their bosses are more adaptive.

The researcher also discovered that the campus and all the profiles evaluated in the study, including age,

gender, and years of teaching experience, revealed no significant variations in the degree of adaptation abilities of teachers. Munda (2021) supported this which found that teachers over 50 had a very high adaptability level compared to other age groups. Furthermore, there was no significant difference in the level of adaptability skills of the teachers based on gender, implying that both male and female teachers have equal levels because they all have the same interpretation. Finally, there was no significant difference in the teachers' adaptability skills based on years of teaching experience; all teachers with different years of teaching experience have equal levels because they all have the same interpretation. Teachers with 16-20 years of teaching experience and more than 30 years of experience showed extremely high levels of adaptability. Teachers with more than 30 years of experience and those with 26-30 years of experience showed extremely high levels of flexibility, whereas those with 1-5 years of teaching experience had the lowest mean. Furthermore, teachers at MNHS got higher mean score than GNHS teachers. It demonstrated that there was no disparity in the teachers' adaptability as to their school. In other words, the two groups of respondents were both highly adaptable.

Finally, the study found no link between teachers' adaptation skills and performance. The variables were not connected linearly. It contradicted the findings of Andres et al. (2021), who discovered that teachers' adaptation skills influence their teaching performance.

CONCLUSIONS

Most of the teachers in the study are women between the ages of 31 and 40 who have been teaching for less than 6 years. It was determined that more female teachers participated in the survey. It also revealed a relationship between instructors' ages and years of teaching experience. Older and experienced teacher-respondents had highest mean scores that the rest of the categories. While MNHS teachers got higher mean score than GNHS teachers, the respondents were both highly adaptable.

Despite the pandemic, the study also found that teacher-respondents do quite well in teaching-related performance. Having ratings between 3.500 and 4.499 necessitates instructors working hard even in all kinds of setting.

The research discovered that teachers had high self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making, competency knowledge, and general flexibility. In conclusion, instructors demonstrate high flexibility in the current learning environment in all aspects.

The hypothesis that there was no significant difference in the degree of adaptation abilities of the instructors based on age, gender, and years of teaching experience was maintained, indicating no difference. It was found that the teachers' profiles and school have nothing to do with their ability to adjust to the new way of learning. The hypothesis suggesting no significant relationship between instructors' adaptability abilities and performance was kept as variables were not linearly connected. The study determined that teachers' performance and adaptation abilities were unrelated; hence, their performance cannot be judged based on how they can change in their environment.

The researcher focused on the profile, flexibility in self-awareness, personal management, problem-solving and decision-making, attitude, understanding of skills, and instructor performance throughout the epidemic. In 2021-2022, the survey was administered to teachers at GNHS and MNHS in the Division of Cabuyao, Laguna. The researcher explored gathering the most recent teacher performance ratings. The study contributed to the literature by demonstrating that instructors' adaptation abilities and performance were unrelated. It demonstrated that these two variables were distinct from one another.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are suggested:

1. Addressing the needs of the other sectors, which had a low participation rate in the study, should be highlighted for future studies to provide an equal representation in adjusting to the learning environment.
2. School principals, supervisors, and higher-ups in the Department of Education are encouraged to collaborate and coordinate to assist instructors in maintaining their outstanding performance in this new mode of learning. Education sector members must work together to help each other adjust to the current setting.
3. It is critical to pursue programs and initiatives that will assist teachers in maintaining their high level of adaptation abilities to keep them engaged and empowered. Teachers must be constantly equipped with the strategic abilities required to perform better.
4. The researcher suggests that other variables related to teachers' adaptability skills be investigated for them to have productive and efficient work performance. Future research may focus on other variables that have a relationship with the study's variables.
5. Future scholars may do research on instructors' adaptation and performance using a larger sample size. They may consider doing district- or division-wide research on the variables. The flexibility of instructors can also be related to other aspects.

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